
Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-Arthritic Polyherbal Formulation: Arthocalm Capsules

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Abstract: The main objective of this article is to formulate & evaluate antiarthritic polyherbal capsules, ArthoCalm. The assay of Curcumin Content in 3 batches of ArthoCalm Capsules was 27.58%w/w, 28.58%w/w & 28.11%w/w, and AKBA Content was 7.06%w/w, 6.89%w/w & 6.96%w/w, respectively. And the amount of curcumin present in ArthoCalm Capsules batches is 153.76 mg, 158.19 mg & 150.25 mg, and the amount of AKBA is 39.36 mg, 38.14 mg & 37.20 mg, respectively. The standardization parameters, including organoleptic evaluation, average weight, weight variation, disintegration time, and moisture content, for the formulated capsules were determined. These results show that the polyherbal formulation ArthoCalm capsules is more effective for the treatment of Arthritis.

Keywords: Arthritis, ArthoCalm Capsules, Curcumin content, AKBA content.

1. Introduction

Arthritis is a chronic autoimmune disease. Arthritis often affects pairs of joints and can affect more than one joint, including the small joints in the wrists and hands. In addition to joint pain and stiffness, people with arthritis may also have symptoms such as weight loss, low-grade fever, and fatigue. It causes the joints to swell and can result in pain and progressive loss of function. Over time, other joints could be affected, such as the shoulders, elbows, knees, feet, and ankles. The most common symptoms a person with arthritis may experience are stiffness in the morning and pain, and swelling of joints in the same joint on both sides of the body. Some possible causes include:

- Genetics: People with family members who have arthritis may be more likely to get it
- Hormones: Female hormones also play a role in diseases
- Viruses or bacteria: Arthritis may be related to viruses or bacteria that you come in contact with during your life.

Arthritis occurs when the system attacks the synovium, the lining of the membranes that surround the joints. The result is inflammation thickening the synovial, which can eventually destroy the cartilage and bone within the joint. The tendons and ligaments hold the joint together, and weaken and stretch. In case of the joint losses, its shape and ligament. Arthritis is a musculoskeletal system disorder following mechanical and biological events that can destabilize normal coupling between degradation and synthesis within articular cartilage. Arthritis can affect individuals of any age, but is more predominant in the age range of 25 and 50 years, with a peak in the age range of 40-50 years. 100 types of Arthritis, of which the most commonly occurring include in arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus and juvenile arthritis. The two main types of arthritis that is osteo-arthritis and rheumatoid arthritis, in which the Indian population has 22-39% and 5%, respectively. The worsening condition of the arthritis requires proper therapy for arthritis, along with the economic consideration for chronic treatment.

In which the systemic drug for the arthritis is also available in the market there its use is limited due to serious side effects upon chronic use. Traditionally, herbal plants have been used both externally as well as internally for treating inflammatory conditions. In which the positive influence of herbal drugs in modifying the pathophysiology of arthritis that case results in a substantial increase in their use as a treatment of arthritis. While the number of drugs available to effectively reduce chronic joint inflammation in the case of arthritis, there should be proof of their therapeutic effects through basic scientific research. This paper deals with a review of herbs showing potential for the treatment of arthritis.

The polyherbal formulation selected for the present study, ArthoCalm Capsules by Suwasthi Intense Health Care Pvt. Ltd., contains some herbal extracts having anti-Arthritic activity. Although Herbal preparations are in demand, they need standardization for better acceptance.

Quantification of Bioactive constituents in the herbal product is an important aspect in developing a method of standardization of herbal medicines. For this purpose, a widely used, modern technique is HPLC. The Curcuma Longa Extract & Boswellia Serrata Extract (AKBA) are both used in ArthoCalm Capsules. Both Extracts are quantified by HPLC.

2. Materials and Methods

Material and Reagents:

ArthoCalm capsules were provided by in in-house production department of Suwasthi Intense Health Care Pvt. Ltd. All other reagents were of HPLC grade or AR grade as per requirement. The Curcumin & AKBA standard of HPLC grade was procured from Natural Remedies Pvt. Ltd., and the analysis was done in the R&D center of Suwasthi Intense Health Care Pvt. Ltd.

Formulation:

Pre-formulation Studies: It includes assessment of different parameters like bulk and tap density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, & Angle of repose in order to determine the flow properties of Polyherbal Powder of 3 batches of ArthoCalm Capsules.

Bulk density

Bulk densities were established by pouring gently 25 gm of the sample through a glass funnel into a 100 ml graduated cylinder. The volumes occupied by the sample were noted carefully. Bulk density was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Bulk density (g/ml)} = \text{weight of sample in gms/volume occupied by the sample}$$

Tapped density

Tapped densities were determined by pouring gently 25 gm of sample through a glass funnel into a 100 ml graduated cylinder. The cylinder was tapped 50 times. Volume occupied by the sample after tapping was recorded, and tapped density was calculated, too.

$$\text{Tapped density (g/ml)} = \text{weight of sample in gms/ volume occupied by the sample}$$

Compressibility index

It is also one of the easiest or trouble-free methods for the evaluation of the flow property of powder by comparing the bulk density and tapped density. A valuable empirical guide is given by Carr's compressibility.

$$\text{Carr's index} = \text{TD-BD} / \text{TD} \times 100$$

Hausner ratio

It presents an indication of the degree of densification that could result from the feed hopper vibration.

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density}$$

Angle of Repose

Flow properties of the physical mixtures of all the formulations were determined by calculating the angle of repose by the fixed height method. A funnel with a 10 mm inner diameter of stem was fixed at a height of 2 cm over the platform. Approximately 10 gm of the sample was passed slowly along the boundary wall of the funnel till the tip of the pile formed and touched the stem of the funnel. A rough circle was drawn around the pile base, and the radius of the powder cone was deliberated. Angle of repose was calculated from the average radius using the following formula.

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

Where, θ = Angle of repose, h = Height of the pile, r = Average radius of powder cone

Preparation of Capsules: The Curcuma Longa Extract (Curcuminoids 95%), Boswellia Serrata Extract (Acetyl Keto Beta Boswellic acid 30%), Piper Nigrum Extract, Curcuma longa Powder, Pineapple extract (Bromelain 2400 GDU/gm), and Zingiber Officinale Extract were finely powdered through a sieve no. 40 and mixed in the proportion as mentioned in Table 1. The polyherbal powder was filled into hard HPMC capsules colored Brown of size "00" by an automatic capsule filling machine (having a capacity of 1.5 lakh capsules in a single operation) in a controlled environment (25°C and less than 60% relative humidity). Capsules containing 550 mg or more, no more than two capsules, should deviate by more than 5%, and none should depart by more than 10%. The filled capsules were de-dusted, sealed, and kept in bottles containing silica gel packets for moisture-free storage.

Table 1: Composition of Polyherbal ArthoCalm Capsules

S. No.	Ingredients	Quantity in mg
1.	Curcuma Longa Extract (Curcuminoids 95%)	200 mg
2.	Boswellia Serrata Extract (Acetyl Keto beta Boswellic acid 30%)	150 mg
3.	Piper Nigrum Extract	10 mg
4.	Curcuma Longa Powder	90 mg
5.	Pineapple Extract (Bromelain 2400 GDU/gm)	50 mg
6.	Zingiber Officinale Extract	50 mg

Capsule evaluation parameters: The parameters, like organoleptic characters, average weight, weight variation, disintegration time, and moisture content, were determined in order to evaluate the polyherbal capsules.

Organoleptic characters: The Polyherbal Capsules were examined for their color and appearance. The color, odor & taste were observed and noted down.

Average weight of capsules: The average weight of 20 capsules was calculated using a digital weighing balance.

Weight variation: Randomly, 20 capsules were selected, weighed individually, and their average weight was compared with the weight of an individual capsule.

Disintegration time: In this method, six random capsules were placed in all six tubes of the Basket rack and dipped into the beaker containing 800 mL of DM water. The Simulated Gastric fluid (SGF) was maintained at 37±2°. The basket was moved 5-6 cm in height, at the rate of 28-32 cycles per minute through a motor-driven shaft. The time was noted at which the capsules passed through a 10-mesh screen and had disintegrated.

Moisture content: The amount of moisture was measured using automatic Karl Fischer titration equipment.

Drug Content:

Curcumin Content By HPLC:

Chromatographic Conditions and Procedure:

Curcuma longa extract was analyzed by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC, Shimadzu P-Series UV system, LC 20AD, Japan), Autosampler- SIL-20ACHT, UV-Detector. The data was acquired on the LC solution

administrator data system (Japan). Shimadzu C18 column (250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) and an isocratic mixture of Tetrahydrofuran: 1mg ml citric acid in water (4:6) used as a mobile phase. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 μ m Millipore filter and degassed by sonication for 30 min. The flow rate was adjusted to 1.0 ml/min. The injection volume was adjusted to 20 μ l, and detection was made at 420 nm.

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Standard solution of Curcuminoids was prepared by dissolving 50 mg in 50 ml acetone (1000 ppm) then took 5 ml of this solution was diluted to 50ml mobile phase (100 ppm) in a volumetric flask (stock solution). 2 ml of the stock solution was diluted to 10 ml mobile phase (20 ppm), 4 ml of the same stock solution was diluted to 10 ml mobile phase (40 ppm), 6 ml of the same stock solution was diluted to 10 ml mobile phase (60 ppm) and 8 ml of the same stock solution was diluted to 10 ml mobile phase (80 ppm) for linearity study.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Took 10 capsules of ArthroCalm and collected the powder in a Petri dish, weight approx. 50 mg of this powder and dissolved in 20 ml of acetone. The sample was sonicated for 20 min. After sonication, the volume was made up to 50 ml with acetone. Then took 1 ml of this solution was diluted up to 50 ml with mobile phase and filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter.

Acetyl Keto Beta Boswellic acid- AKBA Content By HPLC:

Chromatographic Conditions and Procedure:

Boswellia Serrata Extract was analyzed by HPLC, Shimadzu P-Series UV system. C18 Column (250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) and an isocratic mixture of Acetonitrile:0.1% acetic acid in water (90:10) used as a mobile phase. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 μ m Millipore filter and degassed by sonication for 30 min. The injection volume was adjusted to 20 μ l, and detection was made at 250 nm. The flow rate was adjusted to 1.0 ml/min at 0 min, 1.5 ml/min at 5 min, 2 ml/min at 10 min to 30 min.

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Standard solution of AKBA was prepared by dissolving 50 mg in 50 ml Methanol (1000 ppm) then took 5 ml of this solution was diluted to 50ml Methanol (100 ppm) in a volumetric flask (stock solution). 2 ml of the stock solution was diluted to 10 ml Methanol (20 ppm), 4 ml of the same stock solution was diluted to 10 ml Methanol (40 ppm), 6 ml of the same stock solution was diluted to 10 ml Methanol (60 ppm) and 8 ml of the same stock solution was diluted to 10 ml Methanol (80 ppm) for linearity study.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Took 10 capsules of ArthroCalm and collected the powder in a Petri dish, weight approx. 50 mg of this powder and dissolved in 30 ml of Methanol. The sample was sonicated for 20 min. After sonication, the volume was made up to 50 ml with Methanol and filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter.

3. Results and Discussion

Curcumin content in ArthroCalm Capsules by HPLC:

The assay of Curcumin Content in 3 batches of ArthroCalm Capsules was 27.58%w/w, 28.58%w/w & 28.11%w/w. Chromatogram of Curcumin Standard and ArthroCalm Capsule samples is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: HPLC Chromatogram of (A) Curcumin Standard, (B) ArthroCalm Capsule ACC-00001, (C) ArthroCalm Capsule ACC-00002 & (D) ArthroCalm Capsule ACC-00003

Acetyl Keto Beta Boswellic acid- AKBA Content in ArthroCalm Capsules by HPLC:

The assay of AKBA Content in 3 batches of ArthroCalm Capsules was 7.06%w/w, 6.89%w/w & 6.96%w/w. Chromatogram of AKBA Standard and ArthroCalm Capsule samples is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: HPLC Chromatogram of (A) AKBA Standard, (B) ArthroCalm Capsule ACC-00001, (C) ArthroCalm Capsule ACC-00002 & (D) ArthroCalm Capsule ACC-00003

Preformulation studies: Preformulation parameters such as bulk density, tap density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose were studied. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Preformulation Study of Polyherbal Powder of 3 batches of ArthoCalm Capsules

S. No.	Parameter	Standard Limit	ArthoCalm Capsules Batch Number		
			ACC-00001	ACC-00002	ACC-00003
1.	Bulk density	0.5 – 0.6gm/ml	0.5407 gm/ml	0.5277 gm/ml	0.5438 gm/ml
2.	Tapped density	0.55 – 0.65gm/ml	0.5752 gm/ml	0.5653 gm/ml	0.5973 gm/ml
3.	Carr's index	5 – 15%	6.0%	4.0%	8.9%
4.	Hausner Ratio	1 – 1.5	1.06	1.04	1.09
5.	Angle of Repose	< 25	20.44°	22.64°	20.18°

Evaluation of Polyherbal Capsules (ArthoCalm): The polyherbal capsules of ArthoCalm were evaluated for their organoleptic characters, average weight, weight variation, disintegration time, and moisture content. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Evaluation of polyherbal ArthoCalm Capsules

S. No.	Evaluation Parameters	Specification	Observations		
			ACC-00001	ACC-00002	ACC-00003
1.	Colour	Brown Colour	Brown Colour	Brown Colour	Brown Colour
2.	Size	Double zero	Double zero	Double zero	Double zero
3.	Taste of filled powder	Bitters	Bitters	Bitters	Bitters
4.	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
5.	Average weight (mg)	665 – 735mg	687.5 mg	683.5 mg	664.5 mg
6.	Weight Variation	Avg wt. \pm 5%	646-714 mg	646-714 mg	646-714 mg
7.	Average Fill Weight	Avg wt. -130mg	557.5 mg	553.5 mg	534.5 mg
8.	Moisture content	NMT- 6%w/w	3.42%w/w	3.67%w/w	3.29%w/w
9.	Disintegration Time	NMT- 30 min	5 min	5 min	5 min
10.	Drug Content				
	Curcumin Content	NLT- 140 mg	153.76 mg	158.19 mg	150.25 mg
	AKBA Content	NLT- 35 mg	39.36 mg	38.14 mg	37.20 mg

4. Discussion

The organoleptic properties of developed formulation were brown coloured, bitter in taste, and had a characteristic odour. Moisture is one of the major factors responsible for the deterioration of the drugs and formulations. Low moisture content is always desirable for higher stability of drugs. Moisture contents of ArthoCalm capsules, were below 6%. Study of Bulk density, Tapped Density, Carr's index, and Hausner Ratio is important as the density of a powder defines its packaging for individual drugs and formulations. The disintegration time of capsules is 5 minutes, which indicates that the polyherbal formulation is ready to show its activity after 5 minutes. The amount of Curcumin content and AKBA content present in capsules is more than 140 mg and 35 mg, respectively, which indicates that the polyherbal ArthoCalm capsules have a good anti-arthritis activity.

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References

- [1]. Twinkle J Bhatt, Dhruv Mehta, Vipul Nakum, Vivek Desai and Rakesh Sarvaiya: Preparation and evolution of poly herbal formulation For Arthritis, Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, 2022, 11(4) 311-318.

- [2]. Sapna Desai, Ankita Desai, Komal Rahevar, Divyang Patel, Rutvi Patel, Samiya Patel, and Prachi Patel: Formulation and Evaluation of Poly Herbal Emulgel for Rheumatoid Arthritis, *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 2022, 77(1) 80-85.
- [3]. Vigneshwaran L.V., Senthil Kumar M. and Nitheesh Prabhu S: Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Anti-Arthritic Ointment, *Indian Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Biotechnology*, 2022, 10(1) 1-9.
- [4]. Nanthini B, Selvakumari E, Gopal V and Ranganadhan S: Preparation and standardization of poly herbal capsule, *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 2017, 6(3) 739-741.
- [5]. Sumaira Ishaque1, Ghazala H. Rizwani, Huma Shareef, Shahnaz Gauhar, Maryam Ahmed and Raheela Khursheed: Formulation and Pharmaceutical Evaluation of Polyherbal Capsule (Femitex-Sp 4) For Treating Menorrhagia, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2011, 3(5) 149-154.
- [6]. Aulton, M. E., *Pharmaceutics: The Science of Dosage Form Design*. Churchill Livingstone, London 2002, pp. 322-334.
- [7]. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*, 2018, Volume- I, pp. 299-301.
- [8]. Chaturvedi M, Shukla P, Patel R and Saraswat R: Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Capsules Containing *Sauromatum Guttatum* (Wall.) Schott Tubers and Leaves Extracts, *International Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Allied Sciences (IJBPAS)*, 2020, 9(9) 2337-2347.

